

HEPATOPROTECTORS: THE ROLE OF LITHOPROTECTIVE AGENTS IN THE TREATMENT OF LIVER DISEASES

Umirdinova Volidakhon Gofurjonovna¹

Toshtemirova Charos Toshtemirovna²

Chief Specialist of the Primary Expertise Department,

State Institution “Center of Good Practices”,

Agency for the Development of the Pharmaceutical Industry under the Ministry of

Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute²

amirhonumiridinov@gmail.com

toshtemirovac@gmail.com

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Annotation: This article discusses hepatoprotective medicinal agents used in the treatment of liver diseases, with particular emphasis on drugs possessing lithoprotective properties. The mechanisms of action, indications for use, and clinical significance of hepatoprotectors are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the role of lithoprotective agents in preventing the formation of cholesterol gallstones within the biliary system and in protecting hepatocytes. The article is intended for medical students and practicing physicians.

Keywords: hepatoprotectors, liver diseases, lithoprotective agents, gallstone disease, hepatocyte, ursodeoxycholic acid

Introduction: The liver is a vital organ that performs essential metabolic, detoxification, and synthetic functions in the human body. Various infectious, toxic, drug-induced, and metabolic factors can impair liver function. Therefore, hepatoprotective drugs are widely used in modern medicine to protect the liver. Among them, agents with lithoprotective effects are of particular importance.

The Concept of Hepatoprotectors: Hepatoprotectors are medicinal agents that protect liver cells (hepatocytes) from damaging factors, stimulate their regeneration, and improve the functional activity of the liver. These drugs reduce inflammation in hepatic tissue, enhance membrane stability, and exhibit antioxidant effects.

Lithoprotective Agents: Lithoprotective agents are drugs primarily aimed at preventing the formation of gallstones in the biliary tract and dissolving existing cholesterol gallstones. They modify the chemical composition of bile, reduce cholesterol concentration, and improve bile flow.

Mechanism of Action

Hepatoprotective and lithoprotective agents exert their effects through the following mechanisms:

- stabilization of hepatocyte membranes;
- enhancement of antioxidant defense;
- inhibition of lipid peroxidation;
- improvement of the rheological properties of bile;
- reduction of cholesterol synthesis.

In particular, drugs based on ursodeoxycholic acid are considered effective in diseases of the liver and gallbladder.

Indications for Use:

Hepatoprotective and lithoprotective agents are used in the following conditions:

gallstone disease (cholesterol stones);
 chronic hepatitis;
 early stages of liver cirrhosis;
 drug-induced and toxic hepatitis;
 biliary dyskinesia.

Conclusion: Hepatoprotective and lithoprotective drugs play an important role in the комплекс treatment of liver and biliary tract diseases. They help protect hepatocytes, improve bile circulation, and prevent the development of complications. Therefore, these agents are widely used in clinical practice.

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